

State Defense Power Development Management in Supporting National Security of Aerospace Aspects (Air Power)

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Abstract: The government is responsible and obliged to manage and create a strong and highly defensive national defense force through the development of defense forces that are carried out early and continuously. In the context of realizing national security in the aerospace aspect (air power), the main problem faced by the government in developing the national defense force systems from the condition of the state's limited capacity, resulting in insufficient budget allocation support. The logical effort that has been and is being made to solve these problems is to create a basic force with a minimum standard that is absolutely prepared as the main and fundamental prerequisite for the effective implementation of the main tasks and functions of the Indonesian Air Force in dealing with actual threats. The development of national defense forces in the format of minimum basic strength for a certain period of time must continue, in line with various strategic efforts that must be continuously carried out to catch up in the field of defense, by working as hard as possible, thinking, acting, creating, and innovating in an oriented manner. In the realization of the future vision of the defense of the Republic of Indonesia, namely the independence of the national defense industry, until the time comes for the Republic of Indonesia to have an ideal national defense force to protect its national interests, through development management of Air Power.

KEYWORDS –*Management, Development, State Defense Power, National Security, Aerospace*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia with geographical characteristics consisting of a group of archipelago islands, which are located in a cross position with a variety of natural resources and diverse demographics, must be protected and maintained. This condition on the one hand contains great power to be utilized for the greatest prosperity of the people, but on the other hand also implies a big challenge for its management and security which has implications for the need for the development of a reliable national defense force. This is closely related to the substance of a very basic arrangement in the Chicago Convention, which states in the Article 1 of the Chicago Convention 1944 that each State has full and exclusive sovereignty over the airspace above its territory. The Convention establishes rules of airspace, aircraft registration and safety, and details the rights of the signatories in relation to air travel; it also exempts air fuels from tax. The Convention was signed by 52 states on 7 December 1944 in Chicago, Illinois, U.S., and came into effect on 4 April 1947.

Depraetere Christian, in Island Studies Journal May 2008, write about “The Challenge of Nissology: A Global Outlook on the World Archipelago - Part I: Scene Setting the World Archipelago”. In the article Christian said that: islands are the rule and not the exception. One major objective for nissology - defined as the study of islands and islandness - in the 21st century should be to debunk the unfair prejudice that ‘island studies’ continues to suffer at present time. To do so, a systematic treatment of the island phenomenon needs to be undertaken and this should be backed up by substantial theoretical underpinnings. In seeking to turn the dominant continental paradigm on its head, islands not only deserve to be “studied on their own terms”; they

also become the *deus ex machina* of a holistic understanding of the world archipelago and its ongoing globalization. This vision should contribute towards bridging the gap between ‘continentalists’ who tend to consider islands only as epiphenomena of larger land trends, and ‘island studies’ practitioners.

As stated by Divya Srikanth from Rajaratnam School of International Studies in his writing entitled “Non-Traditional Security Threats In The 21st Century: A Review”, published in *International Journal of Development and Conflict* 4(2014) 60–68, the world underwent seismic shifts in the 20th century in the form of two resource-draining world wars, the creation of a bipolar world order, numerous proxy wars, end of the Cold War and emergence of the US as the sole superpower. However, in the 21st century, the rise of non-state actors, impact of intra-state conflicts, degeneration of the environment, sweeping demographic changes and the rapidly burgeoning cyber-warfare arena have replaced inter-state wars as the main threats to a nation’s security in the 21st century. Unlike the preceding centuries, in which the gravest security threats that a nation-state faced were invariably the armies of other states, in the 21st century, this is no longer the case. The emergence of a number of non-state actors, such as terrorist networks, drug cartels and maritime piracy networks, and intra-state conflicts (e.g. civil wars) have assumed importance as new-age threats to the national security of present-day states. Apart from such non-state and transnational actors, the impact of environmental degradation on the future of the nation-state, especially the implications of global climate change, has emerged as a credible and serious threat to the future existence of modern-day nation-states. Demographical changes, such as an aging and/or shrinking population, especially acute in the Western developed countries, have emerged as the one social factor that might influence global power politics in the future. Finally, technological advancements in the 21st century, particularly with respect to the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) revolution, have facilitated the emergence of cyber-warfare and cyber-espionage, triggering the slow shift of the battlefield from land, air, and sea to cyberspace.

Although at this time more and more people from various circles think that traditional threats are unlikely to occur, in fact in some parts of the world, there are still many conflicts between countries that still use traditional military methods and forces. Therefore, preparedness to face traditional military threats must remain a concern and priority for policy makers in the national security sector, so that the state and nation are in a safe, peaceful condition, and the safety and welfare of its people are guaranteed. The traditional deployment of military forces to intervene militarily against other countries with different national interests is not an impossible situation in the future. Military intervention remains controversial when it happens, as well as when it fails to. Since the end of the Cold War, military intervention has attracted much scholarly interest, and it was demonstrated that several instances of the use of force or the threat to use force without Security Council endorsement were acceptable and necessary. Matters of national sovereignty are the fundamental principle on which the international order was founded since the Treaty of Westphalia. Territorial integrity of states and non-interference in their domestic affairs, remain the foundation of international law, codified by the United Nations Charter, and one of the international community’s decisive factors in choosing between action and non-intervention. Nonetheless, since the end of the Cold War matters of sovereignty and non-interference have been challenged by the emergent human rights discourse amidst genocide and war crimes.

Stephen Budiansky in his book entitled “Air Power: The Men, Machines, and Ideas That Revolutionized War, from Kitty Hawk to Gulf War II”, published by Viking Adult (April 12, 2004), stated that: within a decade of the Wright Brothers historic flight at Kitty Hawk, pilots were dropping the first crude bombs out of airplanes in combat while visionaries were predicting that the crushing power of an aerial assault would end warfare as we knew it. Yet for much of the first century of flight the myth of the airplanes unstoppable power often surged far ahead of technological reality. It would take both brilliant new inventions and bold new thinking for air power to triumph at last as it did with such devastating effect in the two Gulf wars. This sweeping history includes the latest inside details of air operations in Afghanistan and Iraq, where precision weapons and unmanned drones quickly determined the outcome of the fight against the Taliban and Saddam Hussein. Stephen Budiansky draws on combat memoirs, government archives, and museum collections to create a sobering and dramatic account of the air wars of the last hundred years. A story of ideas and men, of intricate machines and fierce passions, *Air Power* is an edge-of-the-seat drama of contemporary warfare and technology crafted by one of our most gifted writers.

Roberta Wohlstetter(Author), Thomas C. Schelling(Foreword) in their book entitled “Pearl Harbor: Warning and Decision”, published by Stanford University Press; 1st edition (June 1, 1962), stated that: for decades the controversy has raged: Was the Pearl Harbor disaster a result of criminal negligence by military officers in the Pacific theater? Was it, as some have claimed, a deliberate plot by the President in Washington? It seems unlikely that a country could have so many warnings pointing to the danger, and yet be so unprepared for the event itself. American intelligence could read top-secret Japanese codes and the U.S. was therefore in a position to transmit vital information to American commanders throughout the world. Most of the time Washington was able to predict both Japan's diplomatic moves and its military deployments. But, as this carefully documented book shows, the outlines of danger look sharp today because the disaster has occurred, and an entirely different image emerges upon reconstructing in detail the intelligence picture as it looked to the participants before the event. In 1941 the pieces of the puzzle were dispersed in a number of government agencies. Some were lost in the noise of signals pointing in other directions—toward a Japanese advance southward or into Siberia; some were slowed by the normal barriers of bureaucracy; and some were silenced by security requirements. At the center of the decision no one had completed the puzzle.

Therefore, the state requires a comprehensive defense approach in dealing with every threat by integrating all national forces, both military and non-military forces. The integration of military and non-military forces is the embodiment of the defense system adopted by the Indonesian people, namely a universal (total) defense system.

In book “Advances in Experimental Social Psychology”, April 2014, vol. 49 (pp.219 - 286), Chapter: Threat and defense: From anxiety to approach, Publisher: Academic Press, Eva Jonas (University of Salzburg), Ian McGregor (University of Waterloo), Johannes Klackl (University of Salzburg), Dmitrij Agroskin (all 8 authors) said that the social psychological literature on threat and defense is fragmented. Groups of researchers have focused on distinct threats, such as mortality, uncertainty, uncontrollability, or meaninglessness, and have developed separate theoretical frameworks for explaining the observed reactions. In the current chapter, they integrate old and new research, proposing both a taxonomy of variation and a common motivational process underlying people's reactions to threats. Following various kinds of threats, people often turn to abstract conceptions of reality—they invest more extremely in belief systems and worldviews, social identities, goals, and ideals.

Article 7-10 of Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian National Armed Forces (Army) states that: The main task of the Indonesian National Armed Forces is to uphold sovereignty, maintain the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, and protect the entire nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the state and nation. The main tasks of the Indonesian National Armed Forces are carried out with Military Operations on War (MOW) and Military Operations Other than War (MOOW). The Army is in charge of carrying out the duties of the Indonesian National Armed Forces in the field of defense. The Navy is in charge of carrying out the duties of the marine dimension of the Indonesian National Armed Forces in the defense sector. The Air Force is in charge of carrying out the duties of the Air Force in the field of Defense.

Threats and disturbances to the integrity of the state and nation can be caused by acts of aggression, territorial violations, espionage, sabotage, acts of terrorism, armed rebellion, civil war or communal conflicts, and threats to maritime or air security of national jurisdiction in the form of piracy, weapons smuggling, fire and ammunition, and illegal fishing and theft of marine wealth. Aggression can occur in the form of invasions, bombardments, blockades, armed attacks, the presence of foreign armed forces that are contrary to the agreement, the use of territory to carry out aggression against the Republic of Indonesia, and the presence of mercenaries in the territory of the Republic of Indonesia.

The identity of the Indonesian National Armed Forces is: People's Armed Forces, Warrior Armed Forces, National Armed Forces, and Professional Armed Forces, namely soldiers who are trained, educated, well equipped, do not practice politics, do not do business, and their welfare is guaranteed, and follow the state's political policies that adhere to the principles of democracy, civil supremacy, human rights, provisions of national law, and ratified international law.

In the air dimension, professionalism of Indonesian Air Force is closely related to its posture, which includes its capabilities, strength, and deployment. In terms of **capabilities**, the Indonesian Air Force must have 12 capabilities, namely: diplomacy, intelligence, attack, defense, specialization, security, support, integration of communication and information, cyber, electronic warfare, maintenance, and empowerment of the air defense area. While **strength** is seen in the comparison of combat power and threat analysis. And, **forced deployments** which include air base deployment, air wing deployment, air squadron deployment, air defense radar deployment, maintenance depot deployment, engineering squadron, deployment of air defense battalion and missile units, and rapid action corps deployment.

To meet the needs of the defense posture as referred to above, the Indonesian Air Force strives to continuously carry out various activities as the implementation of a strength development strategy in the form of strength building, strength development, and strength maintenance; capacity building in the form of doctrine, education, and training; preparation of forces including organization, personnel, materials, facilities and services, systems and methods, and budget; and the deployment of forces, especially at the border, conflict-prone areas, and the outer islands.

On the other hand, the Indonesian Air Force also implements a strategy of deterrence, prosecution, and recovery in both MOW and MOOW. Deterrence is carried out when there is no declaration of war, the status of the situation can be civil order, civil emergency, or military emergency. Action is carried out when there is already a declaration of war, carried out with an active defensive strategy and a defense in depth pattern. If the enemy succeeds in seizing and controlling all or part of the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, then a protracted war will be carried out with guerrilla tactics reinforced by reserve components and supporting components. Recovery is carried out based on state political policies and decisions and is related to a ceasefire. Military operations carried out: rearward transfer operations; territorial operations/regional operations of the defense area. Activities: reconstruction, rehabilitation, and consolidation in synergy with ministries/agencies.

Deterrence strategy in MOW manifested in intelligence operations, strategic air attack operations, air resistance operations, information operations, air mobility operations, special air operations, and territorial operations. **The enforcement strategy in MOW** is realized in the form of intelligence operations, strategic air strike operations, air resistance operations, territorial operations, information operations, air mobility operations, and special air operations. **Recovery strategy in MOW** is realized in the form of intelligence operations, information, air mobility operations, and special air operations, and territorial operations.

While the **deterrence strategy in MOOW** is manifested in intelligence operations, resistance air operations, territorial operations, airspace security law enforcement operations, air mobility operations, special air operations and information operations. Furthermore, the **enforcement strategy in MOOW** is realized in the form of intelligence operations, air resistance operations, territorial operations, airspace security law enforcement operations, air mobility operations, special air operations and information operations. And, **the recovery strategy in MOOW** is manifested in the form of intelligence operations, resistance air operations, airspace security law enforcement operations, air mobility operations, special air operations, and information operations.

This strategy is in accordance with the Indonesian Air Force Doctrine (“Swa Bhuwana Paksa”) which will be used to anticipate threats up to in 2045, both MOW and MOOW. To be able to carry out all operational activities as referred to above, the Indonesian Air Force requires special support from the government. The government is responsible and obliged to manage and create a strong defense force and high deterrence through the development of the national defense force, which is carried out early and continuously.

The development of the national defense force includes the development of human resources, natural resources, artificial resources, facilities and infrastructure, defense technology and industry, as well as a value system to improve national defense capabilities. Military instruments are the main instruments of national power in supporting national interests together with other instruments. If non-military methods fail to protect national interests, military force is used as a last resort. In an active defensive pattern, military forces are built to have sufficient deterrent capabilities so that they are respected by other countries. Military forces are built to have high mobility, hitting power, and personnel who have militancy. The development of military capability is

carried out through a policy of building a military strength posture, in addition to considering the country's economic capacity, as well as analyzing the risk of possible threats to the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia.

The appearance of the strength, ability, and title of the national defense force, is manifested in the military defense posture, which integrates the strength, capability, and title of power with the deployment of non-military defense as a unified whole and integrated national defense. The development of the state's defense posture is highly dependent on the state defense budget allocated by the government. The preparation of the national defense posture is long-term and is based on the state's vision in the midst of global competition. In a condition where the state defense budget is not able to support the needs of defense force development, it is necessary to develop an appropriate scenario so that the interests of defense are not sacrificed.

In connection with the things mentioned above, this article was written with the intention of providing ideas for solving problems instate defense power development managementin supporting national security of aerospace aspects (air power).Regarding the development of national defense forces in the context of securing airspace, in the description below, the author explores the direction management of development of national defense forces, the direction of management of developing air forces, the challenges and problems faced, as well as ideas for solving the problems.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative method with a descriptive analysis approach. In qualitative research methods, data are expressed and analyzed in verbal form without using statistical analysis techniques. In this study, the way to obtain data is through direct observation by observing the symptoms or phenomena that focus on the research, supported by interviewing important figures both from the academic environment, as well as the bureaucracy such as the Ministry of Defense and several related Ministries/Institutions. In addition, researchers also collect data through library research.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Management Directionsof National Defense Forces Development

The development of defense forces includes defense systems and strategies, defense capabilities and structures, Indonesian Armed Forces professionalism, and the development of defense technology to support the availability of defense equipment, reserve components, and supporting components. The development of the defense force is directed at realizing a defense capability that exceeds the minimum defense force. The measure of capability that is the direction of long-term development is the defense capability that can guarantee the sovereignty of the state, the safety of the nation, as well as the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia which includes scattered and diverse land areas, including leading small islands, marine jurisdictional areas to include the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of Indonesia,the continental shelf and national airspace. In peacetime, the direction of defense development is to realize a defense capability that has a deterrent effect that is respected at the regional level and supports Indonesia's bargaining position in the diplomatic arena.

Within the complete framework, the national defense system and strategy are continuously refined to realize a universal defense system to achieve the ability to overcome threats and have a deterrent effect. In this system, national defense is designed to have the ability to ward off threats from the outermost part of Indonesia's territory and the ability to Indonesian territory by land, sea, and air, as well as the ability to monitor and protect all resources in Indonesian territory. The capability and structure of national defense is directed to be able to respond to various possible threats, challenges, and actual problems throughout Indonesia. The development of long-term capabilities is adjusted to the geographical conditions and dynamics of society as well as technological developments.

The improvement of the condition and number of defense equipment in each dimension is carried out according to the validation of the capability and structure of the state defense to be able to exceed the minimum defense force requirement. The fulfillment of defense equipment needs is carried out in stages which are

projected to be achieved in 20 years in line with the state's financial capacity on the basis of technological developments, the principle of independence, ease of interoperability and maintenance, as well as strategic alliances. The development of defense equipment is directed at the strategy of acquiring high-tech tools with deterrence effects and meeting basic operational needs effectively and efficiently by utilizing and developing domestic potential, including the defense industry in the principle of sustainability. The pattern of developing state defense forces in order to secure the airspace of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia has so far been implemented through defense development programs and defense support development programs.

3.1.1 National Defense Development Program.

The national defense development program aims to build the national defense force proportionally and gradually in order to realize a professional, effective, efficient and modern state defense force posture with high quality and mobility so that it can be projected in a relatively short time throughout the country, and can be projected throughout the country, quickly developed strengths and abilities in an emergency. The target of this program is the realization of a professional Indonesian Armed Forces as the main component of the national defense function that is able to face any threat to the sovereignty and integrity of the nation in accordance with the development of the strategic environment. The policy direction of this program is to maintain the capability and strength of the Indonesian Armed Forces as well as to improve the maintenance system including its support system in order to maintain the operational capability of the existing main weapon system so that a complete and reliable capability can be realized. Efforts to develop state defense include system development, personnel development, material development, and construction of facilities which are pursued through the development of the defense of the Indonesian Armed Forces Headquarters, the development of land-based defense, the development of marine defenses, and the development of air defenses.

Defense development is carried out by the Indonesian Armed Forces Headquarters as the agency that fosters and uses Indonesian Armed Force through activities to strengthen patterns of defense operations and prepare software related to defense strategies throughout Indonesia. The development of Army Defense is carried out by the Indonesian Army as the core defense force in the national land area through capacity building and strength development aimed at increasing the capability and operational readiness of the army strategic command and assistance and special forces command units as well as regional units throughout the military regional command, both system development, personnel, material and construction of facilities and infrastructure. The development of Marine Defense is carried out by the Indonesian Navy as the core defense force in the national maritime area through efforts to develop capabilities and build strength aimed at increasing the capabilities of the marines with their equipment, warships, and aircraft, as well as complementing and strengthening the implementation of maritime territorial defense, both in the western and eastern regions of Indonesia.

So far, the achievements of the Indonesian Air Force have been in accordance with the demands of the work program that have been set, very effectively and efficiently, giving pride to the citizens of this nation, having an "aerospace wing" that is in accordance with their identity. Nevertheless, in the ideal perspective, the Indonesian Air Force still requires cooperation and hard work across dimensions, across sectors, across ministries and institutions, and primarily requires adequate budget support for the procurement and maintenance of the main equipment of the air weapon system and all of its supporting system equipment, including the readiness of the Air Force personnel or human resources who are an integral part of the air weapon system.

The future projections of the Indonesian Air Force must of course take into account the advances in technology, communication, and information that have entered the era of society 5.0, the era of smart power, because when that time comes, the difference will be felt with the current state of affairs. The spectacular speed in the development of technological progress, communication, and information as has been shown in the acceleration of civilization change that is getting faster and more sophisticated in the history of changing times from ancient times to the agrarian era, then industry, then information technology, and then the era of society 5.0 what is happening at the moment. It is not easy for policy makers at this time to be able to make accurate projections in the field of national defense and procurement of the main equipment of air weapons systems for a period of 20 years or 30 years, because changing times will inevitably bring changes to the needs, technical specifications, and the sophistication of the weapons and the nature of the threats that affect them.

Some of the very proud efforts that have been given by the Indonesian Air Force to the state and nation to maintain the establishment of the sovereign Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, safe from various threats of force using air vehicles in particular, include the following. Air force defense development is carried out by the Indonesian Air Force as the core defense force in the national airspace through capacity building and strength building efforts aimed at increasing the capabilities of operating units, air defense units and special forces in the context of optimizing the air force special troops wing, and strengthen and gradually develop the capabilities of the Indonesian Air Force units within the ranks of operations command I, operations command II, and operations command III. In an effort to strengthen the national air defense system, especially in the eastern part of Indonesia, namely in the context of increasing the capability of air surveillance, identification, interception, and prosecution of air targets, the national air defence IV sector command has been built in stages and has been operating, based in Biak. In addition, the construction of a new radar unit is also carried out in accordance with priority needs, personnel development, and the Indonesian Air Force material development which has been attempted through the procurement of equipment and spare parts for main equipment of weapon system which is directly related to the consolidation of air squadrons, education squadrons, radar squadrons, Indonesian Air Force special troop squadrons, the engineering squadron and the maintenance depot squadron.

In an effort to optimize aircraft operational readiness, the procurement and repair program for all kinds of aircraft has been completed. In an effort to improve the operational readiness of weapons, and in order to increase the strength and readiness of the existing defense equipment has been procured. From the perspective of organizational culture, the presence of personnel, and organizational maturity supported by the Indonesian Air Force Doctrine "Swa Bhuwana Paksa", it demonstrates the ability to carry out tasks with proud performance achievements, in accordance with the targets to be achieved. So, actually the Indonesian people are very optimistic that when the Indonesian Air Force is equipped with its needs, it will be able to carry out heavier tasks more brilliantly, as he has shown in the achievement of the results of his work program so far. With the availability of the main weapon system equipment in the air force at this time, which of course is still very limited and still far from adequate, the competence and spirit of defending the country of all its soldiers as a reflection of a very proud military organizational culture, the Indonesian Air Force has shown its preparedness for any situation when it can be deployed in various assignment fields.

The development of the Indonesian Air Force facilities is prioritized on the gradual construction and rehabilitation of the Indonesian Air Force Special Troop Squadron. In order to increase the ability of strategic air bats to withstand the invasion rate as long as possible outside the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) as a boundary in the buffer field and to be able to overcome 3 crisis areas. In addition, the construction of the Indonesian Air Force facilities is also realized by continuing the construction and rehabilitation of facilities and infrastructure to improve the welfare of soldiers, rehabilitation of facilities and infrastructure of educational institutions in order to improve the quality of the Indonesian Air Force personnel.

Even though the results of research conducted by many institutions at this time show that the most likely threat in the next decade is not a military threat, but once again it is necessary to emphasize on this occasion that vigilance and preparedness must be maintained. Because nothing is impossible in the dynamics of association between nations and the demands of the national interests of each nation are not always the same and in line, and when differences occur which then escalate to more complex and higher conflicts, to armed conflict, military aggression and military invasion is not only word. But the potential threats that can occur, including and not limited to threats using air vehicles, must be faced with air force and capability, with appropriate deployments according to their needs. All of these efforts require a defense posture of the Indonesian Air Force that is reliable, tough, and capable, supported by the main equipment of an adequate air weapon system.

3.1.2 National Defense Support Development Program.

The national defense support development program aims to organize professional modern management and improve the capacity for fostering and utilizing the country's territory, national surveys and mapping, natural and artificial resources, national facilities and infrastructure, science and technology and strategic industry, human resource development, and cooperation in international defense sector. The target of this program is the management of human resources, natural resources and artificial resources to support the

implementation of national defense. The policy direction of this program is to organize citizen development, natural resources, artificial resources, national facilities and infrastructure which can directly or indirectly increase the strength and capability of the main components and reserve components. In the defense support development program, there has been planting and awareness formation of every citizen on their rights and obligations in the defense and security of the state through fostering awareness of defending the state by empowering community organizations. In order to provide direction and guidance for the organizers of the defense function which is essentially to uphold sovereignty, maintain the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and protect the safety of the nation from any threats both coming from outside and arising within the country, a strategic product has been compiled consisting of the national defense doctrine, state defense posture, national defense strategy, state defense white paper, which contains the nature of the threats facing Indonesia, as well as national interests and national defense. As stated in the White Paper on National Defense, the threat faced by the Indonesian people is estimated to be more likely to come from non-traditional threats, both transnational and domestic. Therefore, Indonesia's defense strategy policy to face and overcome non-traditional threats is a priority and very urgent and in its implementation prioritizes the Indonesian Armed Forces by using Military Operations Other than War(MOOW)together with all components of other nations in an integrated effort according to the level of escalation threats faced. The use of the Indonesian Air Force in MOOW tasks is directed at urgent defense purposes, including fighting terrorism, dealing with Aceh and Papua separatist groups, dealing with radical groups, overcoming communal conflicts, overcoming robbers and pirates, overcoming illegal immigration and marine pollution, overcoming logging illegal timber, overcoming smuggling, assisting the civil administration in overcoming the impact of natural disasters, handling refugees, search and rescue assistance, as well as securing peacekeeping tasks.

3.2 Management Directions for Development of Aerospace Strength (Air Power)

Indonesia as an archipelagic country in the Pacific region views maritime/sea security as a prominent regional security issue that will receive continuous attention in the future. The increasingly strategic function of the maritime area in the interests of countries in the world encourages efforts to increase its security. In line with maritime security, the issue of aerospace security is not much different. Based on the Convention on International Civil Aviation, Chicago December 7, 1944, Article 1 states that "Every country has complete and exclusive sovereignty over the air space above its territory". Aerospace is part of the universe which consists of air space and outer space. It gets taller and expands towards infinity. In this view, aerospace has distinctive characteristics that pose challenges for the human mind to conquer and establish it on a very wide spectrum of possibilities. Moreover, with the existence of Law Number 26 of 2007 concerning Spatial Planning, which contains national strategic areas containing defense area content which implies the need for dynamic and static defense area management. Thus, the empowerment of the aerospace area is an effort to foster and empower the element of national aerospace as a reserve component of the air force as well as a component supporting the air force that can support the implementation of the tasks of the Indonesian Air Force and the Indonesian Armed Forces in times of peace and war. This capability is directed at increasing the empowerment of regional aerospace potential from various military components in order to support the country's defense capabilities in the air. Aerospace activities, involving the community and various relevant agencies in the area. Aerospace and airspace is a very important air medium and has strategic value that needs to be secured. Through aerospace, the enemy will be easy to destroy quickly and precisely throughout the territory at any point which is the sovereignty of a country. Therefore, the aerospace and airspace must be secured through air control of the entire area which includes detection, identification, and action.

Indonesia's vast national airspace is a challenge for air defense forces to secure it. This is due to the condition of the defense equipment system, some of which have exceeded and will end their service life. The air defense system has a uniqueness that is very tied to the conditions of operational feasibility determined by the manufacturer, so it is impossible to delay the replacement of such a defense equipment category. In addition to main equipment of armament system whose age is critical, air defense cannot rely solely on the capabilities of fighter aircraft, but must also be supported by remote sensing devices. The need for radar units for air defense has not been fulfilled until now so that observations of air space have not been maximized. The capability and

structure of the air force is directed to provide a high deterrent effect in the field of air defense power with high maneuverability and cruising capability. In the face of actual threats, the capability and structure of the air force is capable of supervising the national air space and the entire territory of Indonesia, able to exceed the minimum requirements for safeguarding national air space, initiating the use of space, capable of carrying out operations and providing support within the framework of the Integrated Tridimensional.

The strength of the Indonesian Air Force is developed by building a defensive air force capable of providing protection for the land and sea dimensions. In the field of organization, the operational strength of the Indonesian Air Force with three air force operations command has not become a force that can at a minimum secure the airspace of the Republic of Indonesia. In order to meet the minimum force, the target of developing the Indonesian Air Force's strength is directed at developing a more rational air force operations command organization, including gradually upgrading its aircraft and defense equipment, most of which are far behind. In this case, fighter planes that have expired are prioritized for replacement. In the area of capability, increasing the attack unit, transport unit, radar unit, and training unit is a concern for improvement. The attack hunting unit was built to meet the needs of nine fighter squadrons consisting of fighter planes with high attack power, supported by reliable support units. The strength of the Indonesian Air Force's Transport Unit is the focus in the implementation of three integrated dimensions military operations. The condition of the Indonesian Air Force transportation unit is very far from the demands of the needs, especially because the existing assets are very old. The construction of the transport unit is carried out by maximizing the procurement of aircraft and supporting equipment from domestic production.

The function of the training squadron must be able to ensure the maximum combat readiness of Indonesian Air Force personnel. Radar units which include point, terminal, and regional radars are increased in range so that the entire territory of Indonesia is within the effective coverage of the radar system being deployed. The addition of a new radar unit is directed to be deployed in areas that do not yet have a radar unit as well as areas that have strategic value. The radar unit was developed through interconnection with the satellite system so as to realize the integration between radar, aircraft, reconnaissance, ships, and rocket systems owned by each force.

The base is gradually increased to support the operations of the Indonesian Air Force by projecting it on the main Base. The development of the capability of the National Air Defense Command is carried out in stages into four Sector Command by maximizing highly capable radar units as well as missile and missile units cannon. Development of air attack repelling capabilities is carried out in order to realize a deterrence strategy that is able to provide maximum protection to Indonesian territory from enemy air attacks. The strength of the Indonesian Air Force Special Troops is maintained in numbers as part of the deterrence strategy. Organizing special troops in three special troops wings to carry out functions as the special troops squadron, stand-alone flight, education functions, anti-terror and protocol guard functions, mainstay in tackling the threat of terrorism.

The capability of the Indonesian Air Force Material Maintenance Command relies on maintenance depots which will then be developed gradually to shift from a human-intensive pattern to a technology-intensive pattern. The educational function carried out by the Indonesian Air Force Education Institute is revitalized so that it becomes a center of excellence and carries out its function as a kitchen to produce quality defense human resources. The revitalization targets are aimed at curriculum, adequate educational facilities and infrastructure as well as the welfare and careers of educators assigned to educational institutions.

3.3 Challenges and Problems Faced

3.3.1 Challenges

Changes in international geopolitics, which are marked by the strengthening of the unilateralist approach, have an impact on the development of the doctrine of preemptive attack, which can penetrate the boundaries of a country's jurisdiction outside the realm of international law. In addition, the strengthening of the military capabilities of neighboring countries, which significantly exceed the defense capabilities of the Republic of Indonesia, has weakened the bargaining power of international diplomacy. Therefore, one of the main challenges in the development of defense forces that must be faced in the future is to build a defense force above the minimum defense force so that it has a deterrent effect in the regional and international regions.

The development of defense forces with deterrence capabilities should have been achieved in accordance with the stages in national development. However, the challenge of national development to restore economic conditions that experienced a severe crisis since 1998 has resulted in a slowdown in development in other fields, including the defense sector. In addition, low-intensity conflicts, including terrorism, separatism, communal conflicts, transnational security threats, and the depletion of state wealth, especially marine and forest products due to illegal acts, have hampered the achievement of the development of the defense force because it takes a lot of attention and costs.

Another challenge in the development of national defense is the demand to build a professional Indonesian Armed Forces so that it becomes a national force capable of carrying out its functions in the era of globalization faced with the nature of increasingly complex threats. Defense efforts to maintain the sovereignty of the state and the territorial integrity of the Republic of Indonesia and ensure the safety of the nation from every threat will be very difficult to do without the support of modern defense equipment. Therefore, the challenge in building a professional Indonesian Armed Forces is essentially building the national defense force by increasing the number and condition of the Indonesian Armed Forces defense equipment to exceed the minimum basic strength in accordance with technological advances. The real condition of the Indonesian Armed Forces at this time must be admitted that it is still below the standard of professionalism. The Indonesian Armed Forces strength in terms of the main equipment of armament systems is faced with limitations and shortages in terms of numbers and unpreparedness as a result of the current main equipment of armament systems being an asset that is outdated in technology, while the regeneration process is running very slowly.

Parallel to these advances in defense technology, other countries are modernizing their defense forces in the defense system, while Indonesia is relatively lagging behind in this field. Indonesia's current backwardness in defense development is basically an accumulation of past national development policies that prioritized the welfare aspect over the defense aspect. As a result, the underdevelopment of defense has unwittingly affected Indonesia's low bargaining position in the international sphere. Even in the scope of Southeast Asia, Indonesia's defense power is far behind by other countries that were previously under Indonesia. In that context, building a professional Indonesian Armed Forces is not only a necessity for the Indonesian Armed Forces, but also the needs of the entire Indonesian nation in elevating Indonesia's bargaining position in the face of rapid competition in the era of globalization. The development of defense forces in the next few years is still oriented towards replacing the Indonesian Armed Forces defense equipment, which in general is no longer feasible to maintain. It will take at least 20 years to regenerate the Indonesian Armed Forces main equipment of armament system which is outdated in technology. Defense efforts to maintain the sovereignty of the state and the territorial integrity of the Republic of Indonesia and ensure the safety of the nation from every threat will be very difficult to do without the support of modern defense equipment. Therefore, the challenge in building the national defense force is to increase the number and condition of the Indonesian Armed Forces to achieve strength beyond the minimum defense force in accordance with technological advances.

3.3.2 Problems

In order to protect the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia for the next several decades, based on the results of an analysis of realistic potential threats, the Indonesian Air Force has, is currently, and will make various efforts to meet the needs for the main equipment of air weapons systems that are ready to be used, as follows: 2010 -2014 air defense systems that are included in the procurement program are 279 units. Then, in 2015-2019 additional procurement of 63 units. And, in 2020-2024, 163 units are planned to be procured. To further carry out continuous procurement with the target of achieving the fulfillment of the main equipment needs of the air weapon system until 2045 as many as 171 units. Thus, the total number of main equipment for air weapons systems that are ready to be used is 676 units.

The problems faced in the development of the air force power include the factual conditions of the existing defense equipment, which generally do not give hope to provide deterrence. Faced with the strength and capability of the countries surrounding Indonesia, the existing air power and the existing radar and missile units are not sufficient to guard Indonesia's air defenses. The current force of 3 (three) operation commands has not fully provided deterrence against possible enemy air attacks. Missile unit elements consisting of radar, cannon, and rocket systems are developed in a reliable system, both attached to the air defense system and to the support

of the communication system, to achieve targets as needed, it requires stages in its continuous development, starting with short-range missile units and medium range and built a cannon system and a rocket system that is integrated with a satellite control system. On the other hand, the capabilities of the Indonesian Air Force are also needed to neutralize enemy forces and as assistance to other elements, including:

- a. Control of the national airspace. National airspace control includes detection, identification, and action. The need for combat air patrol aircraft (Combat Air Patrol / CAP), is calculated by setting a defense radius of around 130 NM, so that mathematically it can be formulated that for a control area of 172,000 Km², 6 aircraft are needed. To secure the airspace over a territorial area of 5,3000,000 Km², 186 aircraft are needed;
- b. Overcoming the three conflict areas (trouble spots). Conflict areas that must be addressed with the Indonesian Air Force minimum basic strength include three trouble spots at the same time, both those requiring MOW and MOOW handling or both;
- c. Security of the Indonesian Archipelago Sea Lane area. The security of the area around the Indonesian Archipelago Sea Lane is carried out by placing fighter aircraft at 7 point positions;
- d. Transport, Reconnaissance, Heli and Train needs. Basically the number of existing squadrons is sufficient, it remains only to fulfill the number of aircraft in one squadron and increase the number of readiness. Deployment tailored to the demands of the needs refers to the development of escalation of threats;
- e. Radar needs. Radar needs are adjusted to the area and capability of radar coverage, the contours of the earth, and the feasibility of placing radars that require altitude;
- f. Missile needs. The need for missiles is adjusted to the escalation of the threat and the availability of the budget.
- g. Base requirements. In order to maintain readiness and operational capability, it is necessary to increase the status of several bases, both main bases and operating bases of type A, type B, type C, and type D;
- h. Needs of the Indonesian Air Force Special Troops. Referring to the tasks and functions of the Indonesian Air Force Special Troops, it is necessary to organize and improve the capabilities of the Indonesian Air Force Special Troops as a special air force unit are ready to carry out ground battles, point air defence, and special tasks in supporting air operations and other Indonesian Armed Forces military operations;
- i. Information technology needs. To support smooth operations in order to achieve success in achieving tasks, an integrated information technology facility is needed, through the construction, development, improvement, enhancement, and optimization of existing facilities as well as integrating the deployed network into an integrated system;
- j. Needs for communication and electronic warfare. It is hoped that the fulfillment of communication and electronic warfare needs will be able to weaken the opponent's communication and electronic warfare capabilities and be able to maintain the effectiveness of using communication and electronic warfare itself and to synergize with the main equipment of armament system strengths;
- k. Maintenance needs. Fulfilling the maintenance needs of main equipment of armament system owned by increasing the ability and development of maintenance, both light, medium, and heavy levels;
- l. Personnel needs. The fulfillment of personnel needs for the organization of the Indonesian Air Force is carried out with a right sizing system, restructuring, technology intensive, and Command and control effectiveness as well as by empowering existing personnel in accordance with the required qualifications and specializations;
- m. Intelligence needs. The fulfillment of intelligence needs which are expected to be able to act as an early detection and sensing tool for early prevention in dealing with any threats to the country, is carried out by developing the Indonesian Air Force intelligence system and capabilities by optimizing special equipment for high-tech intelligence and by gradually equipping sophisticated special material equipment; and
- n. Sensor requirements. The fulfillment of the need for equipment based on sensor technology is carried out in a directed, integrated, gradual, and continuous manner, so that data, objects, locations, and positions of strategically valuable targets can be presented in order to support the main tasks of the Indonesian Air Force.

From the State Expenditure Budgetside, the total defense budget in Indonesia was approximately 87 trillion in 2014. This figure is only 0.8 percent of Indonesia's GDP, but if you look at the trend in recent years, Indonesia's defense budget has increased. By comparison, the average NATO defense budget is 2 percent of GDP. Assuming that Indonesia's defense budget can one day reach the ideal figure of 2 percent of GDP, there is room for continued growth. According to projections made by Jane's Defense Budget, Indonesia's defense budget will double from around 50 trillion in 2010 to around 100 trillion in 2017. However, in terms of percentage, GDP from 2013 to 2017 is still around 0.8 percent. The main problem faced by Indonesia in the development of its national defense force, despite the significant increase in its defense budget, it must be understood that the majority of Indonesia's defense budget is still used for operational purposes, equipment maintenance, and personnel expenditure.

In plain view, the ability and strength of national defense, since the beginning of the New Order until the Reformation Era, has decreased and has no deterrence effect when compared to the quality of capabilities/strengths that the Indonesian nation had in the early 1960s. So that in recent years, the sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia has often been violated by the Armed Forces of other countries. Quantitatively, the current number of Indonesian Armed Forces personnel does not meet the needs of organizational standards, while the procurement of new personnel is only able to maintain the existing strength. With these limitations and also faced with many assignments, efforts to increase the professionalism of personnel through education and training cannot be carried out properly. In the field of weaponry, the main tools of the Indonesian Armed Forces main equipment of armament system which are operated are generally in an old condition and technologically inadequate when faced with possible external threats, thus requiring intensive maintenance and rejuvenation to support tasks that currently have a very high intensity of use. The possibility of a prolonged embargo on imports of military equipment greatly affects the readiness of the Armed Forces main equipment of armament system. On the other hand, the small amount of support for the defense budget and the weak exchange rate of the rupiah against the US dollar greatly affect efforts to achieve the level of readiness of the Indonesian Armed Forces defense equipment and the professionalism of Indonesian Armed Forces soldiers.

The process of implementing the development of defense forces for the Strategic Plan I Period 2010-2014 was not easy, experiencing challenges in terms of budget provision and implementation practices. The challenges faced in using the pure rupiah budget from the State Expenditure Budget include the manufacture of defense equipment which has a very long completion time of more than one year (multiple years) it will be difficult to use the State Expenditure Budget which is effective only for one fiscal year. In addition, the characteristics of a budget whose payments come from the state treasury will put a burden on the second half of the fiscal year. Gradually the government has made improvements to this problem. The large cost of procuring defense equipment, if budgeted for only one year, will erode the cost of capital for other purposes. However, if it is allocated for more than one fiscal year, it will create uncertainty for the budget for the following years. Procurement of defense equipment in US dollars carries the risk of exchange rate differences, in which the rupiah tends to weaken against the US dollar causing the need for an additional rupiah budget to cover the gap in the contract.

3.4 Thinking for Troubleshooting

Based on the description above, a small conclusion can be drawn that in implementing the development of the national defense force, especially in building the air force, there are challenges and problems that are not easy to answer and the needs that must be met so that the Indonesian Air Force can carry out its duties and functions properly according to strategic needs, national interests, and the provisions of laws and regulations. Then, how to build the air force of the state defense force in the context of securing the airspace in conditions of limited capabilities and insufficient budget?

3.4.1 Build Air Defense Minimum Basic Strength (Short Term and Medium Term)

In fact, the strength of national defense is a requirement that must be met by state administrators, even in a weak economic condition, as a prerequisite so that any actual and/or potential threats to the existence of state sovereignty and safety can be effectively overcome. Defense forces must be able to integrate the interests of responding to actual and potential threats proportionally in the defense posture so as to show a balance

between planning for the development of national defense forces in the short, medium term, and planning for the development of national defense forces in the long term.

Basically, the development of the national defense force is directed to be able to ward off all forms of actual threats. The function of military defense in the context of deterrence displays armed strength (hard power), and is manifested in an Indonesian Armed Forces posture that is Tridimensional in nature which describes an Indonesian Armed Forces that is solid, professional, and equipped with adequate defense equipment so that it has a high deterrence effect, both in the form of a strategy of rejection (denial) and strategy of retaliation (reprisal). Threats faced in maintaining state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety are increasingly becoming multidimensional, physical and non-physical, as well as coming from outside and from within the country. The threat of invasion or military aggression from other countries against Indonesia is estimated to be very small. By observing the development of the strategic environment, at this time and in the next few years there is no indication of a conventional military threat that leads to Indonesian territory. However, this conducive condition does not make Indonesia neglect its preparedness in building the nation's capacity to protect the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Therefore, the development of strength in the national defense sector must continue to be prepared by combining military and non-military defense capabilities to ward off every possible threat and if conditions force it, be able to deal with all changing situations. The strength of the national defense cannot be compromised on the grounds of a limited budget, considering the risks faced are fatal to the survival of a country. Thus, as a logical consequence of the development of the national defense force, it implies a guarantee of the availability of the budget support needed to make it happen.

In conditions of limited capacity and insufficient budget to protect the national interest of a country with strong and reliable powers, a distinction must be made between actual and potential threats. Thus the defense force must also be built according to the needs of the threat. The use of minimum basic strength is a logical choice and answers the needs of threats, although it is not an ideal strength, but a form of minimal strength that is prepared in accordance with limited resources still gives hope to overcome the actual threat. The minimum basic strength will give its own meaning to the Integrated Three Dimensional strength posture developed by the Indonesian Armed Forces, namely: the fundamental and main part of the overall system in the smallest possible or required number. In conditions of limited capabilities and insufficient budget, Indonesia does not need to build its national defense strength on par with the defense forces of leading countries in the world, such as the United States, Russia, England, France, Germany, Turkey, China, and other countries with the strongest defense forces in terms of funding and equipment. At present, up to a certain period of time, what Indonesia needs to protect its national interests is a standard of basic and minimum strength of the Indonesian Armed Forces which is absolutely prepared as the main and fundamental prerequisite for the effective implementation of the Indonesian Armed Forces main tasks and functions in dealing with actual threats.

The minimum essential force (minimum basic strength) in the defense sector cannot be separated from the state defense management system which is organized at the level of authority. The elements consist of: (1) elements of human resources, (2) elements of material / defense equipment, (3) natural resources and artificial resources, (4) elements of base facilities, regional training facilities and national infrastructure, (5) elements of the defense industry, (6) elements of the state defense area, (7) elements of the budget. The seven elements in the defense management system are the anatomy of the minimum basic strength in national defense that can be used as a formula for consideration in determining the strength of the Indonesian Armed Forces in the future.

The development of minimum basic forces in the short and medium term is directed at the goal of realizing an air defense force that has the ability to provide deterrence, which, when faced with the strengths and capabilities of the countries surrounding Indonesia, the existing air power and radar and missile units owned are equal, even has the advantage of guarding the air defense of the Republic of Indonesia. In addition, the development of air defense forces in the short and medium term is directed so that the 3 (three) operational commands fully provide deterrence against possible enemy air attacks. Missile unit elements consisting of radar, cannon, and rocket systems developed in a reliable system, both attached to the air defense system and to the support of the communication system, achieve targets as needed through stages in their sustainable development. Short-range and long-range missile units are being built and integrated with the cannon system,

rocket system, and satellite control system, can be operationalized properly. So that the capabilities of the Indonesian Air Force can be used both to neutralize enemy forces and as assistance to other elements.

As a response to the current state of the country which is in limited capacity and insufficient budget, the development of the defense forces of the main component countries, particularly the air force, is projected to ward off actual threats. Its realization is developed through four strategies that are very likely to be implemented in a gradual planning scale through rematerialization, revitalization, relocation, and procurement strategies.

Rematerialization is the fulfillment of the 100% of organization and equipment table and personnel list of Indonesian Armed Forces personnel and material units; revitalization is an increase in unit strata/thickening of units/material levels above it which is adjusted to the development of threats in its territory; relocation is the transfer of units/personnel/materials from one area to the projected flash point area; and procurement is the construction of a new unit and its personnel and defense equipment.

In connection with the four strategies above, it is also necessary to have the courage to carry out eliminations which are strategic and economic actions due to the reasons for not fulfilling the safety and feasibility factors, either through the run-down system (abolition/sudden termination) or through the push out system (phased operational elimination). Procurement policy is oriented and prioritizes "utilization of the domestic defense industry" according to the ability to produce to meet the Indonesian Armed Forces main equipment of weapon system based on operational requirements and military technical specifications that have been set by the user (Indonesian Armed Forces) with a payment scheme using domestic loans by banks. and payments are guaranteed by the government using State Expenditure Budget funds.

The development of the Indonesian Air Force's strength is directed at the organizational, personnel, and material aspects/defense equipment, through the four strategic options referred to above (rematerialization, revitalization, relocation, and procurement). In the organizational aspect, the capability of the Air Force Base and Special Troops is increased. In the personnel aspect, , the projection of the manning of Indonesian Air Force personnel in the 3 Strategic Plans is gradually implemented with the replacement of personnel who are shrinking/retiring, changing groups, and procuring new personnel to maintain balance and maintain the existing composition, the arrangement is directed through relocation, restructuring, and revitalization leading to an increase in solid capabilities people become solid based on technology and manned by high quality personnel (high quality based and merit system) as well as increasing the effectiveness of control commands, followed by the development of the number of personnel adapted to the new main equipment of weapon system

but prioritizing and maintaining the composition that is there is. In the material aspect, the Indonesian Air Force Material/main equipment of weapon system capability has been improved by rematerializing through the maintenance of all aircraft, radar and main equipment of weapon system to 100% of the current condition which is still operational within a certain period of time.

3.4.2 Build an Ideal Air Defense Force (Long-Term)

President Joko Widodo in his inauguration speech as President of the Republic of Indonesia 2019-2024, before the People's Consultative Assembly, said that: our dreams, our aspirations in 2045 in a century of independent Indonesia should, God willing, Indonesia have come out of the income trap middle class. We are currently at the peak of the demographic bonus, where our productive age population is much higher than our unproductive age. This is a great challenge as well as a great opportunity. This becomes a big problem if we are not able to provide job opportunities. But it will be a great opportunity if we are able to build superior human resources. Supported by a conducive political ecosystem and by a conducive economic ecosystem. Innovation should not only be knowledge. Innovation is culture. In a world full of risk, which is very dynamic and highly competitive, we must continually develop new ways, new values. Don't get stuck in a monotonous routine. Breaking the routine is one thing. Increasing productivity is another priority. No longer do our work is process-oriented, but must be oriented towards tangible results.

The essence, meaning and spirit contained in President Joko Widodo's speech are very relevant to the efforts of all components of the Indonesian nation to realize it in various fields of national and state life, including the development of air defense forces in the context of securing airspace. In this regard, all relevant parties must work as hard as possible, harder to catch up in various aspects of air defense power development. Start by thinking in a strategic conceptual framework regarding the stages and methods of achieving goals to create an

independent and respected Indonesia because of the fulfillment of the ideal defense equipment needs for national defense, including aspects of airspace defense. Laws and regulations in the field of defense need to be interpreted and implemented in line with the strategic vision of developing a defense force that is on par with the countries with the strongest national defense forces in the world. All national think tanks such as National Resilience Institute, National Resilience Council, Defense University, and various other universities carry out creative and innovative research in the field of developing national defense forces. Our dream, in 2045, is with the active participation of all components of the Indonesian nation to support the development of an ideal national defense force, by thinking, acting, creating, innovating, oriented towards realizing the vision of a national defense force that is equal to the strongest defense force in the world, so that in securing the airspace, the Indonesian Air Force has the capability:

- a. Adaptive to the development of the doctrine of preemptive attack, which can penetrate the boundaries of a country's jurisdiction outside the realm of international law;
- b. Having the ability to increase the bargaining position in the international diplomacy arena due to the strengthening of the national air defense force which significantly exceeds the defense capability and deterrence effect in the regional and international regions;
- c. Supported by professional Indonesian Air Force personnel so that they become a national force capable of carrying out their functions in the era of globalization, facing the increasingly complex nature of threats; and
- d. Supported by modern defense equipment in accordance with technological advances, and continuously undergoing a regeneration process that runs rapidly, with the ideal number and conditions needed by the Indonesian Air Force to carry out its duties.

IV. Conclusion

In order to maintain state sovereignty, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state, all components of the Indonesian nation are obliged to make every effort to build and foster the capability, deterrence of the state and nation, and tackling any threats. For this reason, all national resources in the form of human resources, natural resources, and artificial resources, values, technology, and funds can be utilized to improve the country's defense capabilities, including to build the national defense force in order to secure the airspace.

1. In order to maintain and protect state sovereignty, the territorial integrity of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from all forms of threats, through deterrence, prosecution and recovery, the Indonesian Air Force requires defense equipment that is in accordance with the standards for securing the airspace of the Republic of Indonesia, but the Air Force is facing problems with conditions of limited capacity and insufficient budget to make it happen. In order to solve these problems, in the short and medium term, as a logical choice of strategy, the Air Force creates a basic force with a minimum, absolute standard that is prepared as the main and fundamental prerequisite for the effective implementation of the Indonesian Armed Forces main tasks and functions in dealing with actual threats.
2. The development of national defense forces in the format of minimum basic strength for a certain period of time must continue and be carried out through the national defense development program and the state defense support development program that has been implemented so far.
3. In line with the development of national defense in the format of minimum basic strength, all components of the nation need to make various strategic efforts to catch up in the field of defense, by working as hard as possible, thinking, acting, creating, and innovating with orientation to the realization of the vision of the defense of the Republic of Indonesia in the future, namely the independence of the national defense industry, until the time comes for the Republic of Indonesia to be ready to have an ideal national defense force and be able to return to its role as a country with the strongest defense force in the world.

REFERENCES

Books

- [1.] Bakrie, Connie Rahakundini. *Pertahanan Negara dan Postur TNI Ideal*. Jakarta: Yayasan Obor Indonesia. 2007.
- [2.] Budiansky, Stephen.,2004.*Air Power: The Men, Machines, and Ideas That Revolutionized War, from Kitty Hawk to Gulf War*. Viking Adult.
- [3.] Hasanuddin, Tubagus. *Arsitektur Keamanan Nasional: Membangun Sistem Kamnas Yang Terintegrasi*, Jakarta: PT. Wahana Semesta Intermedia. 2013.
- [4.] Hasanuddin, Tubagus. *Bela Negara dan Kontradiksi Wacana Wajib Militer Indonesia*, Jakarta: PT. Wahana Semesta Intermedia. 2014.
- [5.] Hermann, Margaret G., and Charles W. Kegley. 1998. The U.S. Use of Military Intervention to Promote Democracy: Evaluating the Record. *International Interactions* 24 (2): 91-114.
- [6.] Karim, Silmy. *Membangun Kemandirian Industri Pertahanan Indonesia*, Jakarta: PT. Gramedia. 2014.
- [7.] Kementerian Pertahanan Republik Indonesia. *Buku Putih Pertahanan Indonesia*. 2014.
- [8.] Prihartono, T. Hari dan Anak Agung Banyu Perwita. *Mencari Format Komprehensif Sistem Pertahanan dan Keamanan Negara*. Jakarta: Propatria Institute. 2006.
- [9.] Suwondo, Purbo S. *Strategic International Chokepoints in the Indonesian Archipelagic Waters*. Jakarta: Legiun Veteran Republik Indonesia. 2004
- [10.] Wohlstetter, Roberta., And Thomas C. Schelling. 1962. "Pearl Harbor: Warning and Decision", Stanford University Press; 1st Edition.
- [11.] Wulan, Alexandra R. *Satu Dekade Reformasi Militer Indonesia*. Jakarta: Pacivis. 2008.
- [12.] Yusgiantoro, Purnomo. *Ekonomi Pertahanan*, Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.2014.

Regulation

- [1.] Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun1945
- [2.] Chicago Convention on International Civil Aviation 1944
- [3.] United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS) 1959
- [4.] United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) 1982
- [5.] Undang-Undang Nomor 39 Tahun 2008 tentang Kementerian Negara
- [6.] Undang-Undang Nomor28 Tahun1999 tentangPenyelenggaraNegara Yang Bersih dan BebasDari Korupsi, Kolusi, dan Nepotisme
- [7.] Undang-Undang Nomor 3Tahun 2002 tentang Pertahanan Negara
- [8.] Undang-Undang Nomor 34Tahun 2004 tentang Tentara Naional Indonesia
- [9.] Undang-Undang Nomor 39 Tahun 2008 tentang Kementerian Negara
- [10.] Undang-Undang Nomor 25 Tahun2009 tentang Pelayanan Publik
- [11.] Undang-Undang Nomor 17 Tahun2011 tentang Intelijen Negara
- [12.] Undang-Undang Nomor 16 Tahun 2012 tentang Industri Pertahanan
- [13.] Undang-Undang Nomor 23 Tahun2014 TentangPemerintahanDaerah
- [14.] Undang-undang Nomor 23 Tahun 2019 Tentang Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Nasional Untuk Pertahanan Negara
- [15.] Peraturan Pemerintah Pengganti Undang-Undang Nomor 23 Tahun 1959 tentang Keadaan Bahaya.

Websites

- [1.] Bissessar, A. M. (2009). *Rethinking The Reform Question*. CambridgescholarsPublishing. Retrieved From <https://Www.Google.Com/Books>
Hl=en&lr=&id=bvuybwaaqbaj&oi=fnd&pg=r5&dq=wog+vs+npm&ots=epl47ifvww&sig=30Bb8rtcliqtz7-Szts299w78ae
- [2.] Christensen, T., & L\ a Egreid, P. (2006). *The Whole-of-government Approach—Regulation, Performance, And Public-sector Reform*. Retrieved From [Http://Bora.Uib.No/Handle/1956/1893](http://Bora.Uib.No/Handle/1956/1893)
- [3.] Depraetere Christian., *Island Studies Journal*, May 2008. “The Challenge of Nissology: A Global Outlook on the World Archipelago - Part I: Scene Setting the World Archipelago” (<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/26569058>)
- [4.] Howe, Neil and Richard Jackson. 2011. “Global Aging and the Crisis of the 2020s.” CSIS. https://csis.org/files/publication/110104_gai_jackson.pdf.
- [5.] Jason, Interagency Administration Jason Marisam
File:///C:/Users/ASUS/Downloads/Ssrn-id2137151%20(1).Pdf
- [6.] Jervis, Robert. 2002. “Theories of War in an Era of Leading Power Peace.” *American Political Science Review* 96:1–14.
- [7.] Management And Peacebuilding. (N.D.). Retrieved November 3, 2016, From [Http://Glossary.Usip.Org/Resource/Whole-governmentapproach](http://Glossary.Usip.Org/Resource/Whole-governmentapproach)
- [8.] Mariya Polner [Http://Www.Wcoomd.Org/En/Topics/Research/Activities-and-programmes/~//Media/799443EF399B48C0B18DA2285B034F36.Ashx](http://Www.Wcoomd.Org/En/Topics/Research/Activities-and-programmes/~//Media/799443EF399B48C0B18DA2285B034F36.Ashx)
- [9.] Roberta Wohlstetter, Thomas C. Schelling. 1962. “Pearl Harbor: Warning and Decision”, Stanford University Press; 1st edition (June 1, 1962), (https://www.amazon.com/Pearl-Harbor-Decision-Roberta-Wohlstetter/dp/0804705984/ref=pd_vtp_scl_2_1/144-4343303-6274130?pd_rd_w=BR6l9&content-id=amzn1.sym.fbd780d7-2160-4d39-bb8e-6a364d83fb2c&pf_rd_p=fbd780d7-2160-4d39-bb8e-6a364d83fb2c&pf_rd_r=KDFYSJQD6EQ23SXGR09T&pd_rd_wg=jajuz&pd_rd_r=c3ec3f1f-8ea3-4571-805c-f94249c26b35&pd_rd_i=0804705984&psc=1)
- [10.] Stephen Budiansky. “Air Power: The Men, Machines, and Ideas That Revolutionized War, from Kitty Hawk to Gulf War II”, Viking Adult (April 12, 2004), (<https://www.amazon.com/Air-Power-Machines-Ideas-Revolutionized/dp/0670032859>)